

Reverting homogenous forest landscapes in a Mediterranean site. Transitioning to mixed oak forests

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ABSTRACT

Initial reforestation efforts in the Western Mediterranean basin aimed to convert degraded lands into forests dominated by native Mediterranean oaks following a successional trajectory in which pine pioneer species were extensively used to ameliorate abiotic conditions. However, the transformation into mixed oak forests has not occurred due to changing land use priorities, land abandonment and lack of active forest management leaving a large extent of homogenous pinewood landscapes. Homogenous forests face significant adaptation challenges in the current climate crisis, including susceptibility to pests, diseases, and catastrophic wildfires. This study explores the use of harvest gaps similar to the establishment cuts of the irregular shelter-wood system (ISS), adapted for Mediterranean conditions to transform pure *Pinus pinaster* reforested stands into mixed-oak forests under the assumption that transforming light-demanding monocultures into mixed forests enhance resilience. The method involves creating small gaps (< 0.02 ha) to avoid natural pine regeneration while allowing for oak establishment and planted oak saplings development. The results indicate that oak seedling survival is higher in gaps compared to control plots, with no significant difference between gap sizes. Pine regeneration density is higher in larger gaps, while oak regeneration density is positively influenced by the presence of harvest residues. Survival of planted oak is high although browsing prevents full height development. Small harvest gaps are effective in controlling pine regeneration while supporting oak survival and growth. However, additional measures like fencing may be required to address browsing. The findings highlight the challenges and potential solutions for transforming homogenous forests into more resilient mixed forests.

1. Introduction

Pioneer functional traits confer *Pinus* genus a preeminent role in reforestation and afforestation programs in the Western Mediterranean basin (Pausas et al., 2004). In Spain, an ambitious reforestation national Plan was designed to convert degraded and marginal croplands into forests, which would follow successional trajectories in which native Mediterranean oaks dominance would increase with time (Pemán et al., 2017). Each intervention was preceded by a detailed study of species autecology in order to plant the right tree in the right place. In areas with severe soil degradation, pine species were selected to ameliorate abiotic conditions and facilitate natural oak regeneration. Once pine stands reached the exclusion phase, oak development was to be promoted by

means of silvicultural treatments (clearing, thinning) or, when necessary, underplanting of oaks. The Plan was a success in terms of reforestation performance (establishment, survival and growth) but the transformation into a conifer-hardwood mixture and a subsequent oak forest did not occurred because of the lack of active management to create suitable abiotic conditions for oaks to thrive. As a consequence, of the more than 3,000,000 ha were planted between 1940 and 1983, nearly 800,000 ha was monospecific Maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* Ait. ssp. *mesogeensis*) afforestations (Solís, 2003).

Homogenous forests pose serious adaptation problems in the current climate crises. Biotic host-specific pests and diseases find continuous forested areas for feeding and reproducing increasing the damage, and longer and heavier drought events are more frequent and are sometimes

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accompanied by heat spells, i.e. mega-droughts. These events, along with the absence of silvicultural measures increase biomass accumulation and create thick fuel that can lead to catastrophic wildfires (Knutzen et al., 2025; Plana et al., 2016).

Silviculturists are aware of this situation and have applied “post-event” restoration practices like species substitution for genotypes and/or species resistant to pests, like in northern Spain, where productive *Pinus radiata* plantations affected by red-band disease (*Dothistroma* needle blight) are being substituted with either native *P. pinaster* or exotic *Cryptomeria japonica* and *Sequoia sempervirens*. However, this strategy is based on resistance to rather than adapting to change (Nagel, 2004). Anticipated alternatives are essential to minimize damage to natural capital, infrastructure and human lives. This involves an active application of adaptive silviculture to multiple demands and changing social-environmental conditions (Achim et al., 2022).

Transforming pure, even-aged stands into more complex structures has been pointed as a valid solution to increase the capacity of forests to adapt and/or recover after harmful abiotic and biotic events (del Río et al., 2021). The silviculture of transformation includes methods to increase forest structural and compositional diversity and complexity (O’Hara, 2001). One of the methods broadly applied in temperate and boreal Western forests are gap harvests of various forms, i.e. group selection or irregular shelterwood, often combined with species enrichment through planting within gaps (Raymond et al., 2009). Opening gaps modifies abiotic conditions by modifying light availability, soil temperature and humidity, but other factors also influence tree regeneration success, e.g. browsers density (Borowski et al., 2021; Leal et al., 2022) or the presence of harvest residues (Rodríguez-García et al., 2007). Application of gap harvest requires decisions on gap size (Kern et al., 2013), number of gaps and time between interventions (opening new gaps or expanding existing ones), as well as the need to leave reserve trees.

Gap harvesting methods are generally implemented to increase tree species diversity and structural complexity by maintaining the original dominant species, i.e. natural regeneration of the main tree species is enhanced but light conditions created within the gap allows for the regeneration or plantation of other species. Experimental designs and experiences across the world follow this pattern (De Frutos et al., 2023). Gap size is determined by the ratio between the gap diameter and stand dominant height. When regeneration is the main goal, the most common ratio values range between 1 and 2.5, being the lower the ratio the more shade-tolerant the species to regenerate (Malcolm et al., 2001). In Mediterranean conditions, larger ratios have been applied to regenerate *P. pinaster* Ait. *mesogeensis*, a shade-intolerant species (De Frutos et al., 2023).

The irregular shelter-wood system (ISS) is silvicultural system developed in Central Europe nearly 100 years ago (Troup, 1928) to manage mixed-species stands and other complex forest structures. The fundamentals of the method include the opening of gaps without the spatial constraints of the selection group methods and without following a fixed size-distributional model. The ISS has gained attention recently in other parts of the world (Donoso et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024; Lussier and Meek, 2014; Raymond et al., 2009; Trerise et al., 2025). Initially conceived to achieve regeneration of mid- and shade-tolerant species, it has never been applied in temperate dry forests, like the Mediterranean biome, where other gap harvest methods, e.g. group selection, have achieved successful regeneration rates of light-demanding species (De Frutos et al., 2023) following the expected outcomes of the gap partitioning theory in which shade-intolerant species would thrive in large gaps, whereas shade-tolerant species would require small gaps or overstory to regenerate (Denslow, 1980; Lu et al., 2018).

In public-owned land, particularly in protected areas of Spain and southwestern Europe, management objective has shifted from regeneration of the dominant tree species to full transformation of pure pine plantations into more complex structures, such as mixed-species Mediterranean forests dominated by oaks. Some attempts to achieve this goal

have included drastic reductions of pine density, including clear-felling. However, shade-intolerant and pioneer shrubs (e.g. *Cistus* spp. and *Erica* spp.), and high levels of pine regeneration have emerged, preventing the desired species substitution. In the context of harvest gaps methods, it remains a challenge whether harvest gaps can be used to prevent, rather than promote, regeneration of light demanding species and whether such gaps can create the optimal environment for oak seedlings to emerge or planted saplings to survive in Mediterranean-type conditions.

Here, we present an adaptation of the establishment cut of the ISS for Mediterranean conditions to transform a pure *Pinus pinaster* stand originated from plantation into a mixed-oak Mediterranean forest. The proposed method will follow in subsequent interventions the expanding gap ISS in which gaps are gradually enlarged until they merge at the end of the transformation period (Schütz, 2002). This was combined with plantation of *Quercus ilex* L., *Q. faginea* Lam. and *Q. suber* L in all possible combinations within the gaps for further assessment of mixing effects. In our experiment, the size of the gaps in the establishment cut is designed to be small enough to avoid natural regeneration of pine but large enough to allow growth and regeneration of Mediterranean oaks species which are less light demanding in line with the gap partitioning theory.

Our expected results are i) significant smaller gaps than usually applied (Gap diameter/Ho ratios between 0.5 and 1) control pine regeneration by reducing light availability, ii) although oak saplings survival rate is high irrespective of gap size, iii) survival and growth performance of planted oaks three years after plantation is higher in the smaller gaps, and iv) even in such small gaps, regeneration is higher in the northern position of the gap.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

This study was conducted in Cabañeros National Park, located in the Montes de Toledo range within the southern sub-plateau of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1). The area represents a typical example of an inland Mediterranean climate, characterized by a prolonged dry season and hot summers, cold winters, and precipitation concentrated mainly in autumn and spring. The mean annual temperature is 14 °C, with average summer highs reaching up to 34 °C and winter lows around 2 °C. In intermediate months such as October, May, and June, average temperatures range between 14 and 15 °C. Annual precipitation varies between 500 and 850 mm.

2.1.1. Experimental design

The experiment was conducted in a *Pinus pinaster* Ait. reforestation located in the northern part of the park. This stand is characterized by uniform tree species and age structure, with little to no understorey vegetation. The experiment involved the adaptation for shade intolerant species of the expanded gap version of the irregular shelterwood system: a silvicultural technique that removes all trees within gaps whose size

Fig. 1. Experimental area in Cabañeros National Park (CNP).

depends on the disturbance regime and the species involved, allowing for differentiated light regimes and regeneration conditions. *P. pinaster* is a light demanding species that has been successfully regenerated using group selection system with gaps ranging between 1.5 and 2.5 times the dominant height (De Frutos et al., 2023). However, the final objective is to gradually substitute the pine plantation by promoting the natural regeneration of oaks and planting oak species within the gaps. In our approach, the gap size is smaller than the size commonly used in similar silvicultural methods.

In our experiment 48 gaps were harvested divided into two treatments. Twenty-four were assigned a low gap-diameter-to-height ratio ($0.5 \times$ dominant height, i.e., approximately 8 m diameter, $\sim 50 \text{ m}^2$, here called treatment P), while the remaining 24 followed a 1:1 ratio (16 m gap diameter, $\sim 200 \text{ m}^2$, here called treatment G). In the latter, a thinning was also applied between gaps to further reduce stand density and improve lateral light entry. All gaps were clear-cut systematically—i.e., without selecting individual trees based on competitive status—and stems were removed from the site. Bark and small twigs residues were left in place.

The 48 gaps followed a factorial design combining two gap sizes and seven planting compositions (three monocultures, three two-species mixtures, and one three-species mixture), each replicated three times. An additional six gaps (three per size class) remained unplanted to serve as controls for natural regeneration. This design resulted in 42 planted and 6 unplanted canopy gaps (Fig. 2). In 16 canopy gaps (Fig. 2), hexagonal wire mesh enclosures (six panels of $6 \times 2 \text{ m}$ each) were installed to reduce browsing pressure in the center of the selected gaps (Supp. Fig. 1).

A total of 3294 planting holes were excavated in the gaps and 243 in the control areas, using a mini-excavator. Planting holes followed a staggered (offset) grid oriented East–West, with 1.5 m spacing between holes and 1.67 m between rows. In the control area (no gap harvest), this layout was maintained as closely as possible given existing vegetation.

One-year-old plants were transported from the Park’s nursery facility, located near “Los Palillos” station. In the harvested gaps, 3294 saplings were planted (1125 holm oaks *Q. ilex* L., 1134 cork oaks *Q. suber* L., and 1035 Portuguese oaks *Q. faginea* Lam.), while 243 saplings (81 per species) were planted in the control plots. Based on the planting density ($1848 \text{ saplings ha}^{-1}$), each large gap contained approximately 149 seedlings, medium gaps about 55, and small gaps 18, adjusted to match the actual area of each opening. Each seedling was protected using a 50-cm perforated plastic tree shelter with a stake, consistent with standard park practices.

Natural pine and oak regeneration was assessed in the nine

unplanted canopy openings, within each opening, 1 m^2 subplots were systematically distributed at 4 m intervals, covering the entire surface. All emerging seedlings were individually tagged and monitored twice a year (spring and autumn) from spring 2021 to spring 2023. For each seedling, emergence, survival, and mortality were recorded. Additionally, visual estimates of rock, herbaceous, moss, and harvest residues cover in percentage were recorded for each subplot during the first survey.

Each canopy opening was divided into five sectors (North, South, East, West, and Center), delineated from a central point using axes at 45° and 135° East. In each sector of the gaps, a hemispherical photograph was taken in May 2023 using a Nikon Coolpix P900 camera fitted with a fisheye lens. Images were processed using Hemiview v2.1 software (Rich et al., 1999) to calculate the Global Site Factor (GSF). In control plots, a single hemispherical photograph was taken per plot under the assumption of homogeneous light conditions.

Planted oak survival was visually assessed in November 2022 and November 2023 (36 months after plantation). Dead and alive saplings were recorded in all gaps with planted oaks. Diameter of root collar in mm (at the base of the sapling without soil excavation) and sapling height (cm) were sampled in five individuals per species randomly collected in the gaps planted with the three oak species and in control plots.

2.1.2. Data analysis

Seedling survival following germination—defined as the time to mortality from the point of emergence—was analyzed using a Cox’s proportional hazard model (CPH) implemented in the *coxph* function found in the *survival* package (Therneau, 2024), which estimates how predictors influence the hazard of death over time (Eq. 1)

$$h(t) = h_0(t) \times \exp\left(\sum_{i=1}^p b_p x_p\right) \quad (1)$$

where $h(t)$ is the hazard function in a survival time t as a function of x_p covariates with an estimated impact b_p ; $h_0(t)$ is the initial hazard at time t .

CPH models assumes that hazards are proportional over time, that a linear relationship in continuous variables exist and that there is a lack of strong influential observations or outliers. We tested all these assumptions using a residual analysis. For the proportionality analyses we used the Schoenfeld residuals to test independence from time. We used Martingale residuals to evaluate linearity and transformed variables to meet normality. Finally, influential observations were identified using deviance residuals and corrected, if needed, using a robust estimation of standard errors as implemented in *coxrobust* package (Bednarski et al., 2025). Results were interpreted in terms of parameter significance at 95 %, global likelihood ratio and hazard ratios or exponentiated coefficients indicating the effect size of predictors. As predictors we included treatment (control as reference, large gaps, small gaps), species (pine, oaks were pooled because of similar autecology and early age performance), the interaction between species and treatment, sector in the gap (north, south, west, east) and continuous covariates global sun factor, soil compactness, percentage of harvest residues, moss cover and stones coverage in regeneration plots.

2.1.3. Data analyses

The survival time can inform us about the process of germination, however, the density of seedlings per unit area after a period of time provides valuable information for forest managers. Because the dataset contained a large fraction of no regeneration values encoded as zero, we estimated the density after 36 months using a zero-inflated generalized linear model (GLMs) with a Poisson distribution using the same predictors as in the survival model. If over dispersion was found, we fitted a Negative Binomial distribution. We used R packages *glmmTMB* (Brooks et al., 2017, McGillicuddy et al., 2025) and *DHARMA* (Hartig, 2024) for

Fig. 2. Experimental setup in Cabañeros National Park to transform pure Maritime pine into mixed oak forest.

model fitting and diagnoses respectively. Final model selection was based on lower AICc values and better diagnoses performance.

Plantation survival (i.e., the proportion of live seedlings relative to those planted) was modeled using a binomial GLM. The same set of predictor variables was included. Finally, sapling diameter at the collar and height were analyzed using GLMs with Gaussian distribution. Fencing was included as predictor. All statistical analyses were conducted in R (R Core Team, 2024). Model selection was based on the lowest value of the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), implemented through the dredge() function from the MuMIn package (Barton, 2025).

3. Results

3.1. Time to death of germinated seedlings

The CPH model indicated that treatment and species were significant variables, whereas all other variables did no influence the survival of seedlings after 36 months. The model diagnostics showed that observations followed a proportional hazard pattern (Supp. Table 1), however one significant observation was detected (Supp. Figure 2) and robust standard errors were calculated (Table 1). The Likelihood ratio test (119.1, p-value < 2e-16) indicated a global significance of the model with two predictors.

In Table 1, the negative coefficients indicate a positive effect of treatments on survival compared to control and that oak seedlings have a larger probability to survive. Compared to pines in control, opening large gaps reduces the hazard (death of seedlings) by 71.1 % (1-HR), small gaps reduced the hazard by 30.1 %. The survival of oaks compared to pines in control areas is about 90.1 % higher (Fig. 3).

3.1.1. Regeneration density

The best fitted model, i.e. with the lowest AICc and DHARMA residual analyses (Supp. Figure 3), followed a zero-inflated Poisson distribution model. Treatment, species and its interaction and the interaction between fresh harvest residues and species were significant (Table 2). Regeneration density was higher in larger gaps for both species whereas large amount of harvest residues highly benefited oaks, especially in large gaps, with no apparent effect on pine regeneration (Fig. 4). Opening small gaps did not have significant effects on regeneration density compared to control plots (sup. Table 2 and Fig. 4).

3.1.2. Plantation performance

Survival rates were similar across species in gap openings regardless of their size, however mortality was significantly higher in control plots being Holm oak, the species with a lower survival rate (Fig. 5). Fencing the inner part of the gaps did not result in any advantage for plant survival. However, fencing had a strong positive effect on collar diameter and high growth for all species (Fig. 6) because of browsing exclusion as it was visible by observed damages in unfenced planted saplings.

4. Discussion

Tree species dominance in a managed landscape is situational to

Table 1

Coefficient and fitting statistics for CPH model. Treatment G indicates ϕ Gap = H_0 , and treatment P indicates ϕ Gap = $0.5 \times H_0$.

Factor	Coefficient	Hazard ratio (HR)	Robust SE	z	P-value
Treatment G	-1.2405	0.28921	0.1044	-11.878	<0.0001
Treatment P	-0.3661	0.69342	0.0635	-5.762	<0.0001
Species (Quercus)	-2.3221	0.09807	0.6297	-3.688	<0.0001

Fig. 3. Mean predicted time-to-death probability of pine and oak seedlings after 36 months. Gap ϕ denotes gap diameter.

Table 2

Analyses of variance (Type III Wald Chi-squared test) for regeneration density (counted seedlings) using a Zero-Inflated Poisson Distribution.

Variable	Chi-square	Pr > Chi-square
Intercept	10.298	0.0013**
Treatment	14.584	0.0006***
Species	20.997	< 0.0001***
Treatment x Species	13.294	0.0013**
Harvest x Species	12.741	0.0017**
Random variance Subplot:Plot	0.112513	
Random variance Plot	0.003359	

* p-value < 0.05

** p-value < 0.001

*** p-value < 0.0001

social and economic needs within the environmental limits. In south-west Europe large scale reforestation programs were conducted in the second half of the 20th century for restoration or productive goals. After decades this action left behind a large fraction of homogenous landscapes with one single tree species which, accompanied in some cases by a lack of management, has resulted in less resilient and fire prone ecosystems.

Maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* ssp. *mesogeensis*) was largely used in those reforestation programs for resin production in former arable lands or for substitution of stagnated Mediterranean oak forests, however, the collapse of the resin market in Europe resulted in abandoned mono-specific stands with pervasive ecological and economic effects (Soliño et al., 2018). Nowadays, the goal for more diverse and resilient forests has gained traction and forest owners promote the transformation of monospecific stands into more complex forest structures.

Here, we presented an experimental setup to transform a *P. pinaster* reforestation into a Mediterranean mixed oak forest. Our approach focused on the establishment cut of and adaptation of the irregular shelterwood system (ISS) to Mediterranean conditions, where light is not the main limiting factor, with the opening of small-sized gaps followed by plantation of oaks within the gaps. To our knowledge, this is the first time that this method is applied in Mediterranean conditions. Regeneration methods are designed to promote the regeneration of the dominant species but here we applied the method to control it. The small gaps (0.5 and 1 times the dominant height) are far from the usual size of gaps created for regeneration purposes (De Frutos et al., 2024, 2023) but

Fig. 4. Simulations of the effect of harvest residues left on site.

Fig. 5. Plantation survival after 36 months. Same capital letters indicate no difference between fenced and not fenced gaps by treatment and species. Same "small" letters indicate no difference between treatments by species in fenced and not fenced stands. Control indicates undercanopy plantation, Gap Ø denotes gap diameter. Note that control plots were not fenced.

only the smaller size (8 m of diameter) showed effective reduction of pine germination success whereas both gap sizes kept survival probability of germinated oaks above 50 %.

Oak seedling establishment in harvest gaps is strongly influenced by

acorn supply, microsite conditions, and seed predation. Here, we tested for changes in light environment and found that gap size did not have a significant effect on the time-to-death probability 30 months after oak germination, although larger gaps had higher survival rates. Gaps often

Fig. 6. Root collar diameter (upper panel) and height (bottom panel) performance by species and treatment in fenced and unfenced gaps. Same capital letters indicate no difference between fenced and not fenced gaps by treatment and species. Same “small” letters indicate no difference between treatments by species in fenced and not fenced stands. Control indicates undercanopy plantation, Gap Ø denotes gap diameter. Note that control plots were not fenced.

have lower acorn densities than closed stands, which can limit initial germination, but survival in gaps tends to be higher as resources are more abundant (e.g., litter cover, minimal disturbance) (Collins and Battaglia, 2008; Kellner and Swihart, 2017; Tinya et al., 2020). However, as noted by Barna and Bosela (2015), oak regeneration is not only dependent on seedling survival, which is mainly driven by light availability, but also on germination, which is suggested to be less influenced by light. Furthermore, acorn dispersal in *Quercus* species tends to be deficient in fragmented landscapes and pine-dominated stands (Ramos-Palacios and Badano, 2014), which may additionally constrain the recruitment process. Although adult oaks are scattered in the stand, oak seedling germination in our experimental site strongly depends on the acorn bank in the soil, but this seems to be limited while other factors like seed predation, browsing, and competition from other vegetation might have reduced germination and establishment rates. The presence of harvest residues positively affected oak regeneration, being the effect stronger in larger gaps, while was not significant for pines. Rodríguez-García et al. (2007) found a negative effect of harvest debris on

pine regeneration density but harvest residues (bark and twigs) can have a mulching effect favoring water infiltration and storage as did the addition of straw mulching in Mediterranean oak experimental plantations (Jiménez et al., 2017, 2014). For pine seedlings, our results aligned with existing evidence that larger gaps promote the survival of pine seedlings after germination (De Frutos et al., 2023). However, the decreasing pattern of time since germination indicates a pulse-like regeneration pattern in which oaks’ instant germination rate is high but long-time survival is low compromising the species substitution. Our results might indicate that spontaneous natural regeneration of oaks is not sufficient to transform *P. pinaster* stands, contrary to other attempts to transform other pine-dominated forests (Dobrowolska, 2006).

Survival of planted oaks was significantly increased in gaps compared to control plots but without difference between gap sizes. In our study, survival rates were higher in gaps for all species indicating the species pool is well adapted. In general, Holm oak survival rate was high in open conditions (Jiménez et al., 2014) whereas cork oak survival rate in plantations was highly variable ranging between 40 % and 97 % (El

Alami et al., 2023; Mehergui et al., 2023). Faginea oak (*Q. faginea*) has been less used in transformation or restoration programs, but Turrión et al., (2022) reported for this species high performance for diameter and height but a low survival rate two years after planting in a post-mining restoration program. However, in our case 36 months after planting the survival rate of Faginea oak saplings was still around 75 %. We suggest that the higher rate of plantation survival found in this study is due to partial light conditions compared to full light environments of degraded sites.

Fencing did not have any effect on planted oaks survival rate, but it notably increased root collar diameter and height growth across all species. Planted oaks in unfenced gaps were protected by 50-cm individual shelters and plants hardly overtopped the shelter height due to browsing as was observed. In Mediterranean environments browsing is considered one of the main barriers for natural regeneration of both pines Zamora et al. (2001) and mixed-oak species (Osem et al., 2015). Velamazán et al. (2018) described that what they called small gap openings (0.05–0.75 ha) were sufficient to avoid habitat creation for browsers to cause damage. Besides consuming acorns and seedlings, ungulate browsing has also been found to reduce growth, preventing saplings from reaching heights that would protect them from herbivory (Leal et al., 2022). Also, such a marked browsing effect is not only a problem due to direct seed predation, but also because of its impact on other species, especially shrubs.

As a management recommendation in this type of forest conversion from high light demanding pine species into mixed Mediterranean oaks the opening of small gaps along with oak species' planting and fencing appears as a good option. However, fencing also allows for the development of shrubs, herbs and pines as observed in the fenced gaps (Supp. Figure 1) indicating that fencing large areas compromise the transformation. There are complex interactions between browsing, fencing and vegetation control like weeding (Walters et al., 2016). Recent studies suggest that the presence of shrubs can generally have a positive effect on oak regeneration by ameliorating microclimatic stress, eg. by decreasing soil temperature, and offering protection against herbivory, but this effect is highly dependent on site-specific abiotic and biotic conditions as well as shrub species identity (Acácio et al., 2024; Capó et al., 2024). Although such multifactorial approach was outside the scope of this work, it deserves future analyses, for example by fencing at the tree level in cage-like structures, however the cost and success of this intervention needs a detailed assessment.

5. Conclusions

Forest regeneration methods encompass a series of activities aiming at emulating natural disturbances to modify abiotic conditions. Light environment is managed to promote natural regeneration of desired species but it can also be used to prevent the establishment of undesired ones. For both objectives, the selection of the dominant species is the key management decision.

Transformation of light demanding monocultures into mixed forests poses challenges for forest managers seeking to transform homogenous forests into more resilient mixed forests. Adapting traditional harvesting methods to achieve both successful oak regeneration and limiting pine establishment is taking advantage of natural dynamics and it is considered here a nature based solution. The study points out the potential of very small harvest gaps (< 0.02 ha) with maintenance of harvest residues to control early regeneration of light demanding *Pinus pinaster* Ait. while allowing for high survival and growth of both natural and planted oaks. However, when other stressors like browsing are present, further actions such as fencing are required to support more effectively the conversion of homogenous forests into more resilient oak-mixed forests.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Concepción Elena Daniela: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Acuña-Míguez Belén:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Jorge Maestre-Villanueva:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Andrés Bravo-Oviedo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.foreco.2026.123592.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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